

类似石墨烯魔角的“魔角公式”

黄山

(芜湖职业技术学院，安徽，芜湖，241003)

摘要：通过对石墨烯魔角推测，猜测其他部分晶体的魔角公式。

关键词：石墨烯，晶体，魔角公式。

我可能意外得到了关于类似于石墨烯晶体的魔角公式，

但是我没有办法做实验去验证，

对于立方、六方、四方、三方晶系，

公式为，（晶胞的棱长 c ） / [（晶胞的棱长 a ） * （层内 $c-c$ 间距） * （ 10^{12} ）] = $\sin$ (旋转角度)，单位是 μm ，

因为立方、六方、四方、三方晶系结构类似，所以我猜测他们都有同样的公式，其他的晶系因为没看到有类似的现象，所以不敢猜测，

我为什么这么猜测呢，因为我猜的石墨烯出现这种魔角现象的原因，为

$$\frac{670}{246 * 142 * \sin(1.1^\circ)} = 1$$

石墨烯的晶系和空间群：[六方晶系](#)，P63/mmm

石墨烯的[晶胞参数](#)： $a=246\mu\text{m}$ ， $c=670\mu\text{m}$ ，

典型的层状结构，[碳原子](#)成层排列，每个碳与相邻的碳之间等距相连，每一层中的碳按六方[环状排列](#)，上下相邻层的碳六方环通过平行网面方向相互位移后再叠置形成层状结构，位移的方位和距离不同就导致不同的多型结构。

上下两层的碳原子之间距离比同一层内的碳之间的距离大得多（层内 $C-C$ 间距= $142\mu\text{m}$ ，层间 $C-C$ 间距= $340\mu\text{m}$ ）。

如果没有把握，可以先从类似石墨烯晶系的晶体开始做起。

参考文献：无。

Similar to the "magic angle formula" of graphene magic angle

HuangShan

(Wuhu Institute of Technology, China, Wuhu, 241003)

Abstract: By speculating the magic angle of graphene, we can guess the magic angle formula of other crystals.

Key words: Graphene, crystal, magic angle formula.

I may have accidentally got a magic angle formula similar to graphene crystals. But I can't do the experiment, dear professor. Would you like to try to verify it? For cubic, hexagonal, tetragonal and trigonal systems.

The formula is: (the edge length of the unit cell c) / [(the edge length of the unit cell a) * (the distance between the layers of $c \text{ murc}$) * (10^{12})] = $\sin(\text{rotation angle})$, the unit is pm.

In a typical layered structure, carbon atoms are arranged in layers, and each carbon is equidistant to the adjacent carbon, and the carbon in each layer is arranged in a Because the structures of cubic, hexagonal, tetragonal and trigonal systems are similar, I guess they all have the same formula. Other crystal systems do not dare to guess because they do not see similar phenomena.

Why do I guess this? because I guess the reason for this magic horn phenomenon in graphene is

$$\frac{670}{246 * 142 * \sin(1.1^\circ)} = 1$$

Crystal system and space group of graphene: hexagonal system, P63/mmm. The unit cell parameters of graphene are as follows: axium 246pm, recorder 670pm.

hexagonal ring. The carbon hexagonal rings of the upper and lower adjacent layers are shifted to each other through the direction of the parallel network, and then superimposed to form a layered structure. Different azimuth and distance of displacement lead to different polymorphic structures.

The distance between the carbon atoms of the upper and lower layers is much larger than that of the carbon in the same layer (intra-layer C_{murc} distance = 142pm, interlayer C_{murc} distance = 340pm).

If you are not sure, you can start with crystals similar to graphene crystals.

Reference: none.